

Image Encryption and Decryption Using Threads

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Abstract:

In today's world, most of the communication is done using social or electronic media. Data Security is widely used to ensure security in data communication, storage of information, and in network transmission. Symmetric key cryptographic algorithms have been used as a standard for transferring blocks of data securely. The available Advanced Encryption Standard algorithm is used for text data and it is also suitable for image encryption and decryption to protect confidential image data from unauthorized access. The proposed method in which image data is an input to AES Encryption to obtain the secured/encrypted image and an encrypted image is an input to AES algorithm for decryption to get the decrypted or original image. The method comprises the implementation of the 128-bit AES for image encryption and decryption. An image is encrypted and decrypted in sequential and parallel methods and also measures the time for encryption and decryption of an image. Threads have been used to increase the system performance.

1. Introduction:

Securing image data has become increasingly important for many applications like video conferencing, secure facsimile, medical and military applications, etc. It is hard to prevent unauthorized people from eavesdropping on any communication system including the Internet. Symmetric key cryptography provides a method for securing and authenticating the transmission of information over insecure channels. It enables us to store sensitive information or transmit it across insecure networks so that unauthorized persons cannot read it. Thus, image information transmission has increased rapidly and image encryption technology has drawn more attention.

Images are generally a collection of pixels. encryption is the process of transforming a piece of information (plain text) using an algorithm to encrypted form (cipher text) to make it unreadable by anyone except those possessing special knowledge, usually referred to as a key. The reverse process of transforming cipher text to plaintext is known as decryption.

With the fast progression of data exchange in electronic media, information security is becoming more important in data/information storage and in data/information transmission. Transmission of sensitive data over the network had emphasized the need for fast and secure digital communication networks to achieve the requirements for secrecy, integrity and non-reproduction of exchanged information. Nowadays, image encryption schemes include two processes: substitution and diffusion. The substitution stage permutes all the pixels as a whole, without changing their values. In the diffusion stage, the pixel values are modified sequentially so that a tiny change in a pixel spreads to as many pixels in the cipher image as possible.

The two processes can achieve a satisfactory level of security. The encryption process scrambles the content of data such as text, image, audio, and video to make the data unreadable, invisible or incomprehensible during transmission. The encrypted form of the information is then transmitted through the insecure channel to the destination. At the intended recipient side, the information is again converted back to an understandable form using a decryption operation.

Encryption may be used to prevent unauthorized access to transmitted or stored data, to prevent the analysis of transmitted data, any modification of the data stream, denial of transmission service, and unauthorized connections.

The main scope is to protect data while transmitting in the Internet network channel and from hackers or attackers and to reduce the volume of data during encryption and decryption to minimize the execution time. Here to protect the image data, each pixel information of an image is altered or changed as per the procedure. Hence without knowing the proper procedure, hackers can't modify or hack the data.

2. Literature Survey:

Encryption of binary and grey-scale images based on SCAN patterns: It converts 2D images to a 1D list and employs a SCAN language to describe the converted result [4]. The main drawback is that image compression is not considered and is computationally slow.

Advanced Encryption Standard: To tackle these problems, systems based on advanced encryption standard was proposed. AES is a very fast symmetric block algorithm especially by hardware implementation [1]. The AES algorithm is used in some applications that require fast processing such as smart cards, cellular phones, and image-video encryption.

The work done by Ahmad Abusukhon and Mohammad Talib [9]. In their Algorithm, there are mainly two levels of data encryption. The levels of encryption are performed on the receiver side and decryption is performed on the client side. In the _rst level i.e. Text-To-Image Encryption each letter in the text _le is transformed into three random integers say R for Red, G for Green, and B for Blue where each random number ranges from 0 to 255. The three random numbers represent one pixel in the image _le. In their algorithm, they generated a random pixel (R, G, and B values calling them RGB values) for each letter. During this process the random numbers RGB for all letters are combined and stored in one string, user provide key to transform the plaintext into cipher text. The result of this process is a two dimensional array or Matrix of Pixels (MP) in which each 3 contiguous columns in a given row represent one letter.

In order to make it difficult to attack the data they execute the second level of encryption, here they determine the number of times the matrix is shuffled [2]; say N. where N is equal to the number of columns of MP. Each time the matrix MP is shuffled two random numbers are generated say R1, and R2, where R1 represents a row/column number and R2 represents another row/column number. R1 is replaced by R2 and vice-versa. The Shuffled matrix, say SP, is sent to the client. On receiving SP, the client uses key 2 to retrieve the original matrix MP, and then each pixel in MP is decomposed into R, G, and B values. Then using key 1 each 3 contiguous values (R, G, and B) are transformed to a specific letter.

Praveen.H.L,H.S. Jayaramu,.Z.Kurian [10] Has developed a model that can easily encrypt the images obtained from satellites. Even If faulty data occurs the satellite does not have to wait for a long time to receive the next data. To prevent this error-free encryption scheme is proposed in On-Board. They also state that AES provides an error-free encryption system and error is much more reduced even in radiation in satellites.

3. Methodology:

Implementation of image encryption is done by using AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) algorithm, which is accepted as a symmetric cryptography standard for transferring block of data security. The available AES algorithm is used for text data and it is also suitable for image encryption and decryption to protect confidential image data from unauthorized access. The proposed method in which the image data is input to AES encryption to obtain an encrypted image, and an encrypted image is the input to AES decryption to get the original image. AES algorithm is not only for the text data but also applied for images, usually image processing deals with an image, which is composed of many image points. The image points, namely pixels, spatial coordinates that indicate the position of the points in the image, and intensity values. The image is encrypted using AES. The encryption process is iterative. Each iteration is known as a round. For each round, 128-bit input data and 128-bit key is required. That is, we need 4 words of key in one round. So the input key must be expanded to the required number of words, which depends upon the number of rounds. the process is done. In the AES system, the same secret key is used for both encryption and decryption. So it provides simplicity in design. Image encryption and decryption are implemented by using Python language. This is sequential execution. The time is measured for both encryption and decryption of an image.

In parallel execution, threads have been used for the process. Threads are called light-weight processes and they do not require much memory overhead. They are cheaper than processes. The thread has an instruction pointer that keeps track of where within its context it is currently running. The image is divided into an equal number of parts and each divided part of an image is assigned to each thread and run those threads to encrypt and decrypt an image simultaneously. By using threads, we can reduce time duration of encryption and decryption of an image.

The output of each round serves as input of next stage. In reverse, the decryption

Figure 1: General Block Diagram of Image Encryption and Decryption

Flowchart Representing Encryption and Decryption of an Image Using Threads Encryption

An image is encrypted in parallel by using threads. An image is split into several equal parts and assigned to each part of an image to the threads and the encryption of each part of an image simultaneously. Threads are used to increase the performance of an encrypted algorithm. Figure 2 is the flowchart showing a step-by-step procedure for the encryption process. The image is decrypted in parallel by using threads. An image is split into several equal parts and assign each part of an image to the threads and perform the decryption of each part of an image simultaneously. The decryption of an image using threads is shown in Figure 3. Threads are used to increase the

performance of the decryption algorithm. In general thread creation for encryption and decryption is done using programming abilities without the use of extra hardware components.

Figure 2: Encryption of an image using threads

Figure 3: Decryption of an image using threads

4. Implementation:

The image is first read (Figure 4 shows the input image) and the image has been broken up into a list of pixel values and then appended to a string. If each tuple value is three digits long then a hundred is added to each RGB value. An image is encrypted using the AES algorithm so that the length of an image should be a multiple of 16. An encrypted image is constructed by hexlifying and replacing asciipher characters with numbers. Check the last pixel RGB value of a constructed encrypted image, if it is less than 3, add I digit into it. Figure 5 shows the split image and encrypted image and then an encrypted image is saved in the specified directory. The given image is divided into several parts and each part is assigned to an individual thread. The content of each thread is decrypted separately, finally, all the threads are combined and the result is saved. Figure 6 shows the decrypted image.

Figure 4: Input Image.

Figure 5: Input image and Encrypted image

Figure 6: Encrypted image and Decrypted image

5. Time Analysis

Time is calculated for both encryption and decryption processes by calculating the start and end time of the process. The sequential method takes more time as the size of the image is increased. The time taken for encrypting and decrypting an image of different formats with varied dimensions, which is processed serially is shown in table 1.

When an image is encrypted and decrypted using threads, an improved performance is obtained compared to the sequential method. Table 2 shows the time taken for different image encryption in parallel execution using threads.

Using threads an execution time can be reduced, such that it reduces half of time compared to the sequential execution.

Table 1: Sequential

Image	Dimensions (width*height)	Time taken for encryption	Time taken for decryption
a.png	556 x 544	1.67 sec	0.83 sec
C1.png	238 x 239	0.34 sec	0.16 sec
Cc1.jpg	556 x 544	1.70 sec	0.85 sec
cc.jpg	850 x 1280	6.07 sec	2.95 sec
Cute.jpg	479 x 720	1.98 sec	0.95 sec

Table 1 and 2 show that encrypting and decrypting images of different formats and the same dimensions take the same time. However encrypting and decrypting images of the same or different format and different dimensions varies in time.

From this, it is observed that the time taken for the process is increased when the size of the image is increased. Thus the time analysis for image encryption and decryption is graphically represented as shown in the below figure 7. This snapshot shows the analysis of time variation for different formats and sizes of images.

Table 2: Time taken for image encryption and decryption

Image	Dimensions (width*height)	Time taken for encryption	Time taken for decryption
a.png	556 x 544	1.67 sec	0.83 sec
C1.png	238 x 239	0.34 sec	0.16 sec
Cc1.jpg	556 x 544	1.70 sec	0.85 sec
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Figure 7: Time taken for image encryption and decryption

6. Conclusion

In the digital world nowadays, the security of digital images is becoming more and more important, since the communications of digital products over open networks occur more and more frequently. A general guideline about cryptography is described here. Cryptography protects information by transforming it into an unreadable format. Only those who possess key can decipher the image into the original format. Cryptography is a particularly interesting field because of the amount of work that is, by necessity, done in secret. Internet and other forms of electronic communication become more prevalent.

A successful implementation of AES algorithm is one of the best encryption and decryption standards available in the market. The encryption and decryption process has been implemented sequentially as well as in parallel. And time is calculated for each process of image encryption and decryption. Using threads, it is possible to achieve parallelism to improve the performance.

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